

EmpowerUs

Socio-Economic Empowerment
of Coastal Communities

Policy Brief

Coastal Transition Mechanisms

How to better integrate Europe's coastal communities and the Blue-Green Transition

Coastal communities have ideas and plans on how to redirect the blue economy to support thriving societies, but how can EU Member States better support bottom-up transitions?

What transition means to coastal communities

Six coastal communities in the EmpowerUs project, under the banner of Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs), targeted a shared vision: **to redirect the blue economy to support a thriving coastal community**. Following a process of co-creation with EmpowerUs researchers and local partner organisations, the six communities experimented with solutions and interventions through pilots in their TCLs. While the pilots were specific to local context, three shared strategies were employed to realise the vision for sustainable transition:

1. Widen the users of the sea constituency
2. (Re)claim blue economy benefits and wealth locally
3. Identify (infra)structures that promote local vitality

Strategies	TCL Initiatives
<p>Widen the users of the sea constituency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foregrounds nature connectedness and (re)establishing a constituency of users of the sea who recognise their role in ocean health and their own dependencies on oceans and coastal areas. • Emphasises socio-ecological connections, including public processes to reach groups that have not historically participated in coastal and marine planning or the blue economy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local community development plan in Cape Dolos, Cyprus to operationalise a vision for sustainable coastal use. • Interactive app, NaturCap, launched to highlight the natural and cultural heritage values in Cap de Creus, Spain's MPA.
<p>(Re)claim blue economy benefits and wealth locally</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targets an increase in financial and socioeconomic benefits and wealth generation from blue economy activities. • Focuses on civic engagement while also questioning and critiquing current practices and status within local development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building capacity within the social enterprise sector to expand local engagement and ownership in Connemara, Ireland. • Strengthening Åland's water owner and fisher relations to co-create strategies for healthy fisheries and increased biodiversity.
<p>Identify (infra)structures that promote local vitality</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognises the intention to alter (social, political, economic) structures and encourage infrastructure development to benefit coastal communities. • Addresses migration and retention, connectivity (access and mobility dimensions), and those seeking to build viable and vital, inhabited coastal communities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of bicycle paths re-connecting lakes to the city to support recreation and wellbeing in Burgas, Bulgaria. • Identifying needs and solutions for transport, cultural heritage, and local livability among Træna, Norway's community members.

EmpowerUs findings show that such strategies can only succeed if principles of blue justice are addressed: recognitional (acknowledging diverse groups and knowledge systems), distributional (ensuring local communities benefit fairly), and procedural (ensuring meaningful participation in decision-making).

Those working in and with coastal communities recognise a range of drivers of change, from climate change impacts and biodiversity loss to changes broadly attributed to globalisation. The breadth of contributing factors was notable throughout the project and was powerfully communicated in the EmpowerUs photovoice project (Figures 1 and 2) that allowed coastal community members to express concern about climate change, infrastructure development, and the critical condition of the ocean through photos and accompanying narratives. Coastal communities also face challenges similar to other rural and remote places, such as the impact of social service centralisation and other peripheralising actions.

Nonetheless, these local everyday experiences of what transition looks like does not always fit the current landscape of funding and policy actions. Increasingly transition policy and debate has become almost exclusive to action on climate change and carbon neutrality. Although climate change impacts are at the forefront of coastal communities' concerns, transition is embedded in other social, cultural, political, and economic trends and local challenges due to their physical and social geographies. Across the TCLs, processes succeeded when trust between communities and local authorities was built and when local knowledge directly influenced pilot design. In contrast, when engagement stayed symbolic or could not be translated into action, communities experienced frustration and lost motivation. As transition has increasingly been tied to low-carbon futures and related sociotechnical systems transformations, the specifics of the coastal community situation may be lost.

Coastal communities in many respects have two targets:

1. How to adapt and withstand the impacts of climate and ecological change
2. How to co-determine and benefit from the expanding blue economy, as well as the green agenda.

Figure 1.

"This is a picture of my beloved beach that I pass by on my walks... It is also a place where I feel worried about the sea, algal blooms and the climate catastrophe that is slowly washing over us. Why can't we refrain from predatory fishing, fish farming, ferry traffic for pleasure? Why can't we settle for less? With better."

- Photo and quote by a coastal community member for the EmpowerUs photovoice activity.

Figure 2.

“Seeing how many different creatures live in the sea, one can understand the impact we have on the environmental changes.”

– Photo and quote by a coastal community member for the EmpowerUs photovoice activity.

Local, bottom-up initiatives would benefit from sustained support

When met with questions about sustained impact and their ability to alter systems and practices limiting coastal community sustainability, local partner organisations reflected that many of their initiatives would benefit from prolonged (financial) support. They wondered whether they could pursue the next phase of their initiatives (e.g., realisation of a local, spatial plan) or continuing effective digital tools (e.g., further development of the NaturCap portal and app) without such support. Our results underscore that without sustained financial and institutional backing, inclusive transition processes risk backfiring; rather than strengthening collective agency, communities may become disillusioned if their contributions do not lead to visible and lasting change.

Thus, the dilemma for the EU and Member States as they seek a just, sustainable transition, is how to further support locally led coastal community transitions through EU-level investments and programs. The European Green Deal includes financial programs to address green transition through its Just Transition Mechanism’s three pillars: the Just Transition Fund (JTF), The InvestEU Just Transition scheme, and Public Sector Loan Facility (PSLF)[1]. As a requirement for access to funding, member states must designate regions and make Territorial Just Transitions Plans (TJTPs) within their cohesion policies and engage in a dialogue with the EU Commission.

The Just Transition Mechanisms program primarily targets challenges stemming from phasing out fossil fuel-related activities and decarbonisation. While it appears that assistance to EU regions active in fossil fuel extraction, production, and refinement is the main target, we argue for wider inclusion of coastal regions on account of their needs and evidence of initiatives on program priorities including: biodiversity, ecosystem restoration, urban renewal and regeneration, social infrastructures, green mobility, and up-/re-skilling in green-blue sectors. As evidenced by the pilot in Cyprus, local communities in coastal regions that may already qualify as beneficiaries under the JTM due to a strong presence of carbon-intensive industry[1], face difficulties engaging with planning processes and accessing potential resources for sustainable development at local, national, and EU levels. Furthermore, climate action and carbon-neutrality can be achieved through nature-based solutions such as ecosystem restoration presenting opportunities for coastal communities to develop and benefit.

[1] This policy brief centers on the EU’s Just Transition Mechanisms program and its related funds, which are accessible for EU member states. Norway, which hosted one of the EmpowerUs TCLs, does not qualify under this policy, but is part of the InvestEU program, which seeks to fund similar sustainable transition initiatives.

[2] The Vasilikos Power Plant in the region is mentioned in the Cyprus TJTP from 2021, p. 7, but ultimately was not included as a site of action in the final plan.

Most importantly, as the pilots and initiatives of EmpowerUs' six Transition Coastal Labs demonstrate, action from locals and community anchor organisations show promising mechanisms on the ground – initiatives, civil society networks, partnerships, social innovations – that ought to be scaled and sustained through EU-level initiatives such as the Just Transition Mechanisms. Supporting such bottom-up initiatives could also potentially serve to aid in the development of future TJTPs and subsequent monitoring and evaluation of transition efforts.

Recommendations

To those responsible for identifying and developing Territorial Just Transitions Plans (TJTPs) within EU member state regions:

- Target coastal regions as ripe for transition assistance and experienced in locally initiated mechanisms that promote just, sustainable transitions.
- Recognise the importance of the 'green-blue' interface in actions of the European Green Deal and the new European Ocean Pact. Not only do coastal communities want to guard against the impacts of climate change, they also want to benefit from the EU's promotion of the sustainable blue economy along their shores.
- Support coastal community actions that are tangential to the goals of carbon-neutrality and elimination of fossil-fuel based economies and address other challenges within transition (e.g., biodiversity promoting initiatives, offshore energy sector up-skilling and collective asset management, green mobility networks that benefit coastal community residents and visitors).
- Sustain local initiatives with continued support and encourage initiatives that began within EU-funded research to expand through follow-up funding, within the Just Transition Mechanism's three pillars or in a similar policy.

And to coastal community leaders:

- Contact those responsible for initiating TJTPs and work with regional and member state level planners to discuss Just Transition Mechanism program options.
- Leverage coastal community successes in building resilience, like the EmpowerUs TCLs, by matching such bottom-up initiatives with top-down policies and programs.
- Ensure that participation goes beyond symbolic inclusion and provides community members with real agency by granting them access to resources, decision-making arenas, and long-term institutional support.

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